

Table 2. Average outcrossing rates (%) observed, by entry and treatment.^a

Pollinated accession	T0	T1	T2	T3	Av (by entry)
BG 90-2	0.83	0.50	0.25	0	0.40
Tojo	0.08	0	0	0	0.02
CI 8898-2	0.08	0	0	0	0.02
Secano de Brazil	0.83	0.25	0	0	0.27
Red Rice	0.92	0.50	0	0	0.35

^aSee Fig. 1 for treatment details.

2. Outcrossing rates (%) observed for the different variety × planting design combinations.

The latter trait appeared to be the key trait for the ability to receive exogenous pollen. Treatment T0 was the only one where outcrossing was observed for all varieties; the outcrossing rate was found to be more correlated to stigma exertion ($r = 0.977$, $P = 0.004$) than stigma length ($r = 0.650$, $P = 0.25$). Only BG 90-2, the variety with the most exerted stigma, was cross-pollinated in treatment T2. Outcrossing rate was related to the proximity of male and female plants.

The highest outcrossing rates were observed in T0, where panicles were clipped together (0.08–0.92%). All female varieties showed cross-pollination in this design. The second highest frequency of hybrid seeds was observed in T1, where male and female plants were alternated (0–0.5%). Very few hybrid seeds were observed in T2 (alternate rows). No hybrid was observed in T3 (side-by-side plots).

No outcrossing was observed in T3, which mimics the field design used by the IRG to regenerate seeds. The experiment did not show that outcrossing does not occur during seed regeneration, but it strongly suggested that if outcrossing occurs, it occurs at a rate much lower than the 0.9% observed when panicles are clipped together. Moreover, during normal seed regeneration, seeds are harvested only from the four middle rows out of the eight rows of each plot to decrease the risk of outcrossing. Overall, results did not suggest any need to modify the design for the next regeneration cycles.

Results from T1 showed that seed mixtures can be a significant source of outcrossing and must be avoided. Also, multiplication plots must be carefully monitored to discard plants grown from seeds left from previous experiments.

This study also demonstrated that cross-pollination can occur in farmers' fields where intentional or accidental varietal mixtures are grown, and can contribute to the overall evolutionary process of rice genetic resources. ■

Genetic research

Phylogenetic relationship of genus *Oryza* as revealed by RAPD analysis

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The agronomically important genus *Oryza* L. includes some 20 wild and 2 cultivated species and is divided into four complexes based on morphological and cytogenetical studies. New molecular approaches, such as restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP), internal transcribed spacer (ITS) sequencing, random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD), and chloroplast sympo sequence repeats (cpSSR), have been increasingly employed to assess phylogenetic relationships of the genus, but controversy still exists with regard to species relationships. This study applied RAPD technology to determine the phylogenetic relationships of *Oryza* and evaluate the value and limitation of this technology in phylogenetic studies.

Total DNA was extracted from fresh or dried leaves of 36 accessions representing 23 *Oryza taxa* and 1 accession from *Porteresia coarctata* and *Leersia hexandra* (see table). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) RAPD was carried out on a Rapidcycler (ATC) in a volume of 10 μL , containing 1.2 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ primer, 5–10 $\text{ng } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ genomic DNA template, 50 mmol L^{-1} Tris HCl (pH 8.3), 0.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ BSA, 2 mmol L^{-1} MgCl_2 , 0.5U Taq DNA polymerase, 200 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ dNTP, 1% Ficoll, and 1 mmol L^{-1} tartrazine. The first program was two cycles of 1 min at

94 °C, 10 s at 35 °C, and 20 s at 72 °C, followed by 45 cycles of 2 s at 94 °C, 10 s at 35 °C, and 1 min at 72 °C. The reaction was held at 72 °C for 4 min at the end of the cycles. The RAPD products were electrophoresed in 1.5% agarose gels and then stained with ethidium bromide.

Of the 30 randomly selected primers, 16 (OPL-01, 02, 03, 05, 07, 08, 10, 11, 13, 14, 16, 18, 19, 20, and OPY-06 and OPY-08) successfully showed amplified interspecific polymorphism. RAPD bands were scored as present (1) or absent (0), each of which was treated as an independent character regardless of its intensity. Inconsistent bands were excluded from the data analysis. Data were compiled in a binary matrix for similarity-based analyses using the program of NTSYS-pc (Version 2.02a). The SIMQUAL program was used to calculate Jaccard's coefficient, a common estimator of genetic identity, or to estimate interspecific relationships. Cluster analysis using the similarity estimates was performed with the UPGMA method.

The 16 RAPD primers produced a total of 368 fragments, ranging from 200 to 2,000 bp. A high degree of polymorphism was revealed by a large number of fragments, including some species-specific or genome-specific ones, indicating the usefulness of RAPD variation in polygenetic studies of rice species. The dendrogram (see figure) generated from UPGMA agreed well with the current grouping of *Oryza* species by Vaughan (1989), but with some exceptions. All species with AA genome formed a single group, corresponding to the *O. sativa* complex. Species with BB, CC, BBCC, and CCDD genomes formed a different group, corresponding to the *O. officinalis* complex. The *O. ridleyi* and *O. meyeriana* complexes were included in the third group. *O. brachyantha* was grouped with *O. schlechteri*, and then joined *Porteresia coarctata* and *Leersia hexandra* to form another cluster (see figure).

The cultivated *O. sativa* subsp. *japonica* and subsp. *indica* were closely

Accessions and origin of *Porteresia*, *Leersia*, and *Oryza* species used in this study.

Taxon	Accession no.	Genome	Country of origin
<i>O. sativa</i> subsp. <i>indica</i>	951001	AA	China
<i>O. sativa</i> subsp. <i>japonica</i>	951002	AA	China
<i>O. nivara</i> (1)	100918 ^a	AA	Cambodia
<i>O. nivara</i> (2)	100195 ^a	AA	Myanmar
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (1)	940135	AA	China
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (2)	940331	AA	China
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (3)	940332	AA	China
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (4)	102186a	AA	India
<i>O. meridionalis</i> (1)	103317a	AA	Australia
<i>O. meridionalis</i> (2)	103321a	AA	Australia
<i>O. glumaepatula</i> (1)	103810a	AA	Venezuela
<i>O. glumaepatula</i> (2)	100969a	AA	Surinam
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	103056a	AA	Mali
<i>O. barthii</i> (1)	101257a	AA	Chad
<i>O. barthii</i> (2)	104140a	AA	Cameroon
<i>O. longistaminata</i> (1)	104075a	AA	Nigeria
<i>O. longistaminata</i> (2)	101207a	AA	Côte d'Ivoire
<i>O. punctata</i> (2x) (1)	104071a	BB	Cameroon
<i>O. punctata</i> (4x) (2)	105607a	BBCC	Chad
<i>O. minuta</i>	101082a	BBCC	Philippines
<i>O. officinalis</i> (2x) (1)	940130	CC	China
<i>O. officinalis</i> (2x) (2)	940198	CC	China
<i>O. officinalis</i> (4x) (3)	105112a	?	Philippines
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	105182a	CC	Sri Lanka
<i>O. rhizomatis</i>	103421a	CC	Sri Lanka
<i>O. alta</i>	105143a	CCDD	Guyana
<i>O. latifolia</i>	105141a	CCDD	Costa Rica
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	105669a	CCDD	Brazil
<i>O. australiensis</i>	105263a	EE	Australia
<i>O. meyeriana</i>	104990a	GG	Malaysia
<i>O. granulata</i> (1)	100879a	GG	China
<i>O. granulata</i> (2)	940208	GG	China
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	100877a	HHJJ	Malaysia
<i>O. longiglumis</i>	105148a	HHJJ	Indonesia
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	105151a	FF	Sierra Leone
<i>O. schlechteri</i>	?	?	Papua New Guinea
<i>Porteresia coarctata</i>	104502a	?	Bangladesh
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>		?	China

^aMaterials obtained from IRRI with International Rice Genebank collection numbers.

related to their putative ancestors, *O. nivara* and *O. rufipogon*. One accession of *O. nivara* showed a higher affinity to *O. sativa* than to *O. rufipogon* or other *O. nivara* accessions. It was difficult to separate *O. nivara* from *O. rufipogon* based on the RAPD variation. This supports the results from rDNA ITS sequence analysis (Y. Zhou et al, unpub. data). Two accessions of *O. glumaepatula* showed clear differentiation from *O. rufipogon* or *O. nivara*, suggesting its independent taxonomic status. The African cultigen *O. glaberrima* closely clustered with its progenitor *O. barthii*, supporting the hypothesis that the Asian and African cultivated rice were domesticated independently. The subgroup of *O. meridionalis* and *O. longistaminata* was relatively separated from the other AA

genome species, which agrees with the treatment of *O. meridionalis* and *O. longistaminata* as independent species.

In the second largest group with BB, BBCC, CC, and CCDD genome species, two accessions of diploid *O. officinalis* (CC) from China were clustered with *O. minuta* (BBCC), whereas another tetraploid accession from the Philippines clustered with *O. eichingeri* and *O. rhizomatis*, indicating remarkable differentiation between the diploid and tetraploid *O. officinalis*. Three South American species with CCDD genomes clustered together with the CC genome species, suggesting close affinity to the CCDD and CC genome species.

Noticeably, the EE genome *O. australiensis* formed an independent group, strongly indicating its unique origin and differentiation from other

Genetic evaluation

Identification of an alternate cytoplasmic male sterile source in rice

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Research is in progress in China, at IRRI, and elsewhere to diversify sources of cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) in rice.

To study gene action in high-yielding rice varieties of diverse origin, 13 genetically distinct parents were selected from nine clusters, comprising 56 rice genotypes of different ecogeographic origin, formed through Mahalanobis D2 statistics. Selected parents were subjected to full diallel crosses and F_{15} plants were raised. Observations were taken on yield components.

Among 156 F_1 progenies, we obtained two highly sterile F_1 progenies from the crosses Vytilla-3/IR36 and Vytilla-3/Hraswa (Vytilla-3 is an improved saline-resistant rice variety bred for Kerala conditions and Hraswa is an extra short-duration rice variety—70-75 d—recommended for cultivation in Kerala). The F_1 progenies of their reverse crosses—IR36/Vytilla-3 and Hraswa/Vytilla-3—were fully fertile. This suggested that Vytilla-3 possesses sterility-inducing cytoplasm. Percentage of pollen sterility was estimated using iodine potassium iodide solution; 70% pollen sterility was found in both crosses using Vytilla as the female parent.

Among the 100 BC_1F_1 progenies from the cross Vytilla-3 \times IR36 [(Vytilla-3 \times IR36) \times IR36], 50% pollen sterility in 52% of the plants and 80-82% pollen sterility among the rest was observed. The segregation of F_2 progenies of the same cross (Vytilla-3 \times IR36) was also analyzed for pollen sterility. Of the 78 F_2 progenies, 4 plants showed 100% sterility and 74 plants showed sterility ranging from 3% to 92%.

F_2 progenies of the cross Vytilla-3 \times Hraswa were also analyzed for pollen sterility. The plants also exhibited a high range of pollen sterility (from 5% to 80%).

Dendrogram produced from UPGMA cluster analysis of 38 accessions of *Porteresia*, *Leersia*, and *Oryza* species based on RAPD variation patterns. Accession number and origin of species followed the arrangement in the table.

species in the *O. sativa* and *O. officinalis* groups. *O. ridleyi* and *O. longiglumis* were closely related to each other and formed a group. In the *O. meyeriana* complex, one accession of *O. granulata* from China clustered with *O. meyeriana* and another one from India with *O. ridleyi* and *O. longiglumis*, although the *O. ridleyi* and *O. meyeriana* complexes had genome-specific repeated

sequences to distinguish one from the other. *O. brachyantha* and *O. schlechteri* were unexpectedly clustered together. This result was different from previous reports. Furthermore, *O. brachyantha* and *O. schlechteri* showed higher affinities to *Porteresia coarctata* and *Leersia hexandra* than to other species in the genus *Oryza*, and the four species unexpectedly joined together. ■